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LABORATORY APPLICATION OF CHEMICAL GERMINATING PREPARATIONS AGAINST WHEAT FUNGI CAUSING FUSARIUM DISEASES

Khaytbayeva N.,

Tashkent state agrarian university

Bababekov Q.,

Quarantine and plant protection

Leading Researcher of SRI

Rakhmanov J.

Quarantine and plant protection

Leading Researcher of SRI

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Abstract

In this article, the effectiveness of chemical inseminators against species of the genus *Fusarium* isolated from wheat was studied in the laboratory. In the research, fertilizers approved for use in the republic were used in laboratory conditions on an artificial nutrient medium with the sowing of *Fusarium* fungi in the middle part of a Petri dish, around which seeds treated with fertilizers were planted. And in the control version, untreated seeds are sown. It has been experimentally proved that the most effective seed growers are "Maxim", "Seles-Top", "Fundozol", "vitovax". When treated with these fungicides, the seeds had good germination and suppressed the growth of a pathogenic fungus. In the control variant, fungi on the surface of the seeds and inside the seeds were isolated in an artificial nutrient medium and negatively affected the growth and development of the plant.

Keywords: chemical germinating preparations, wheat fungi, fusarium diseases

Introduction

Based on information in scientific sources and in the list of fungicides allowed in Uzbekistan, there is no data on the action of fungicides recommended for the growth and development of fusarium lily species that provoke fusarium disease, in which many fungicides against fusarium root rot are allowed. These drugs include Fundozol, Vitovax, Maxim, Seles-Top, seeders. There are very few fungicides that completely chemicalize wheat grains from fusarium to the ripening period. The degree of effectiveness of the existing fungisidlan against pathogenic microorganisms is 60-70%, depending on the number of namions in the presence of signs in the field of rid (Gagkaeva, 2015).

The reason for the low effectiveness of fungicides lies not so much in the ineffectiveness of the active substance in the composition of the fungicide (there are many effective drugs against seed infection), but in the very complexity of the method of chemotherapy of the grain and the plant itself, its flower during the growing season.

The main difficulty in preparing the dressing from the chokeberry from fusarium:

- this is the prevalence of diseases in all plantings;
- a long period of plant resistance to infection;
- very rapid penetration of spike infection;
- circumstances such as the fact that the ear is not completely covered with the treated preparation, and that short-term acute feeding cannot be done after treatment, reduce the effectiveness of the control measure.

During the spraying of fungicides, external factors (harm and humidity), the degree of resistance of the plant to diseases, the type and norm of the fungicide,

the duration of fungicidal treatment, the sensitivity of the pathogen to fungicidal effects and the effectiveness of the biological characteristics of the plant act on the plants. pathogenic races are different.

Due to the absolute absence of varieties resistant to laryngeal fusarium, the use of fungicides against fusarium is extremely necessary in regions favorable for the widespread spread of the disease, and in those where epiphytotic morbidity of the disease is observed.

When evaluating the comparative effectiveness of fungicides used against laryngeal fusarium, the following indicators should be taken into account:

1. Determining the degree of reduction of the spread of fusarium in the articular ear;
2. Finding ways to reduce the level of infection of the articular grain;
3. Determination of the degree and amount of increased top dressing under the influence of fungicides;
4. Determination of a method for reducing the accumulation of the amount of metabolites characteristic of fungi in the composition of wheat grains.

When monitoring and evaluating the fulfillment of these requirements, attention should be paid to the presence of the following indicators;

1. Focusing on the degree of contamination of the infectious environment.
2. Comply with the methodological requirements for the use of pathogenic, herbal and fungicidal agents.
3. Accurate analysis of the results of the study.

Therefore, the scientific justification of measures to combat infection in seeds, timely implementation of measures to combat infected plants, the main

phytosanitary measure limiting the ingress of infection from the soil into seeds is being considered, which has a significant economic effect of reducing the harm from the disease.

Research results:

In the experiment, the effect of the fungicides Maxim, Seles-Top, Fundazol, Vitavax seeders from chemical seeders in relation to fungi provoking fusarium wheat in the laboratory was studied. The causative agents of wheat fusarium were planted in the nutrient medium in the middle part of the Petri dish with mushrooms *F. graminearum*, *F.avenaceum*,

F.culmorum, seeds treated with seeders were planted around them. The experiment was observed for 1 month, and the degree of action of each fungicide was recorded. The fungicides studied in the experiment for seeds have shown that wheat is effective against fungi of the genus Fusarium. No infection was observed in the seeds of the experimental variant, and the Petri dish also blocked the growth of mushrooms planted in the middle. In the control variant, when planting without seed treatment, the fungi in the seedbed grew, covering the seeds, which led to rotting of the root and stem as the seeds germinated.

1 fig.

The effect of fertilizing fungicides on the growth of fungi of the genus Fusarium

In these pictures, you can see the effectiveness of germinating fungicides in relation to fungi that provoke fusarium wheat. The seeders tested in the experiment Celestop, Maxim, Vitavax, Dalvex, Fundazol blocked the growth of the pathogen. In the control variant, infection in the seed and internal seed infections were released in seeds planted without fungicide treatment and negatively affected the germination of the plant.

The negative effect of fungicides on the growth of fungi of the genus *Fusarium*

№	Names of seeders and flow rate	Species of the genus <i>Fusarium</i> diameter of the formed colony, cm		
		<i>Fusarium avenaceum</i>	<i>Fusarium culmorum</i>	<i>Fusarium graminearum</i>
1	Maksim XL 035 FS, 3,5% sus.k. (25 + 10 g)	0,5 c	0.6c	0.5c
2	Dalvaks 34% s.sus.k. (170 g/l + 170 g/l) 2,0-2,5	1.5 c	1.3c	1c
3	Vitovaks 200 34% s sus.k. (170 g/l + 170 g/l) 2,5	0.02c	0.05c	0.03c
4	Seles Top 312,5 FS,sus. κ.(262,5 g/l + 25 g/l + 25 g/l) 1,0-1,8	0,7 c	0.5c	0.5c
5	Fundazol 50% n.κ. (500 g/kg) 2,0-3,0	0.03c	0.02c	0.04c
6	Control	7c	6.8c	7.7 c

From the data in the table, we see that a total of 5 seeds were studied in the experiment, all of which had a negative effect on the growth of *Fusarium* fungi, which provoke fusarium wheat disease.

In conclusion, the systematic implementation of measures to reduce the infection of wheat with fusarium disease, the medicinal use of fungicides before sowing seed grain allows storing seed material in good conditions during the growing season and after harvesting top dressing. The result obtained in this experiment shows that when sowing seeds by treating them with effective seed drills Selestop, Mchim, Vitovaks, Dalvaks, Fundazol, not only infection in the seedbed will have a good effect in preventing transmission and damage to plants by soil infections.

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